

CELEBRITY AND TESTIMONIAL ADVERTISING OF LUSH AND DARLING HAIR PRODUCTS: THE ANATOMY OF INFLUENCES AND BUYER BEHAVIOUR

Efetobor, O. Elijah, PhD.

Associate Professor of Mass Communication, Department of Mass Communication,
Joseph Boakai College of Social and Management Sciences, Gregory University, Uturu
Abia State, Nigeria
e.efetobor@gregoryuniversityuturu.edu.ng, +2348032941977

Dr. Andrew C. Apeh, PhD.

Department of Mass Communication, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT),
P.M.B 01660 Enugu State, Nigeria
chiahalam.apeh@esut.edu.ng, +2348033713541

Abstract

Advertisements through the use of celebrity endorsement and testimonials have been useful in creating product awareness and perception in the minds of target customers in recent times, just as advertisers try to use the powers therein to leverage the image and characteristics of the celebrity to promote product brands. Today, testimonial of products and services in advertising has become an important and integral aspect of modern-day advertising. Amongst others, this study was designed to check the extent to which purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are based on celebrity and testimonial advertisements. Anchored on the frameworks of Reference Group Theory and The Source Credibility Theory, the study adopted the descriptive research design, while the survey research method was used in this study. Based on the statistics obtained from the National Population Commission, the population of the study is 257,589 (the total population of females in the Umuahia metropolis, making up Umuahia North and Umuahia South Local Government Area, based on the 2006 population Census figure. Accordingly, a sample of 384 was drawn using the *SmartSurvey* online sample size calculator. A questionnaire was used for collecting quantitative data from the sampled respondents. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Evidence from research data shows that celebrity endorser credibility and testifier have a positive effect on consumers' advertisement recall and purchase intention for Lush and Darling hair products. Based on the findings, we concluded that it will be easy for product manufacturers, wholesalers and retailers of hair products to influence the purchasing behaviour of consumers by building consciousness and sustainable insights in the minds of their consumers using celebrity endorsement, more especially the celebrities that are trustworthy, attractive, and with the requisite expertise. To remain successful and competitive, it was suggested amongst others, that hair product marketers should aggressively implement the use of celebrity endorsement attributes in the advertisement of their products as a business strategy.

Keywords: Celebrity, Testimonial, Advertising, Anatomy, Influences, Buyer Behaviour

Introduction

Advertisement through the use of celebrity endorsement and testimonials has been found as a useful means of creating product awareness and perception in the minds of target customers. Product users, particularly young ladies, see celebrities as role models and opinion leaders due to their social status and fame. They, according to Okorie, Oyedepo & Akhidenor (2012) tend to emulate these celebrities' lifestyles; the way they dress, the way they talk and even look like them physically.

An advertisement from celebrities is not only effective as it captures the attention of the consumers to buy the product being promoted but also creates a long-lasting memory in the minds of consumers as this will influence the consumers to purchase the product repeatedly (Owusu-Mensah, Nimssah and Mensah, 2013). On the other hand, consumer behaviour is the study of how individual customers, groups or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants.

It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions (Smriti Chand, 2018). By understanding what causes the consumers to buy particular goods and services, they will be able to determine— which products are needed in the marketplace, which are obsolete, and how best to present the goods to the consumers.

In today's society, women have become fashionable, and various hair products have hit the marketplace. One such product is the Darling or Lush hair products. These products have gained an appreciable market share in Nigeria. Celebrity Endorsement is a powerful tool by which advertisers try to leverage the image and characteristics of the celebrity to promote a brand. This makes the advertisement lively, attractive, interesting, attention-getting and effective as well. The intense use of celebrity endorsement as an advertising tactic has increased considerably in the past few years; celebrities have been used to promote various kinds of products and services across all industry categories.

The use of celebrity endorsements in advertising has become a trend and a perceived winning formula for corporate image-building and product marketing. As existing media get increasingly cluttered, the need to stand out has become paramount and celebrities have proved to be the ideal way to ensure brand prominence.

In the twenty-first century, most likely every individual is influenced by promotions, in particular when it involves their favourite celebrity. The latter is known as celebrity endorsement. Testimonial of products and services in advertising has become an important and integral aspect of modern-day advertising, as advertisers often believe that a product or service will have more sales once a celebrity is involved. Companies spend huge resources on celebrities to endorse their products or sponsored message on television, radio, newspapers, billboards, the internet, and mobile phones in the hope that such an endorsement will induce a favourable attitude towards the brand by increasing consumers' preference for the brand.

Today, celebrity or testimony adverts enhance the purchasing intention, behaviour, and disposition of users (Rai & Sharma, 2013). Soliciting celebrities is an established tool in marketing and advertisement (Kaikati, 1987). It began in the eighteenth century and continued to the present day while witnessing drastic changes. Nowadays, it is one of the key promoting tools in numerous business fields. It can influence the purchasing choice of an individual either positively or negatively depending on three factors: credibility, appeal, and power (Jatto, 2014).

Since ancient times, marketers in Nigeria have adopted the use of celebrity (Christian, Entertainment Industry, Sports, and Fashion stylists among others) endorsement as a marketing communications tool. Though it was not common in the days of old when the first celebrity endorsement took place in Nigeria, the practice is known to have existed in the country for several years. If a celebrity is endorsing or the business is selling the product of a well-known person or entity, then people assume they must be a good company to deal with. Nigeria has quite several celebrities, who have endorsed several products and services. Examples of some of the early endorsement deals in the country were Sunny Neji, Omotola Jalade Ekeinde and Jide Kosoko endorsement for Chivita Juice Drinks, Kate Henshaw for Onga Maggi, Pastor E. A. Adeboye (G.O. of Redeemed Christian Church of God) and Funke Akindele for Lagos State Inland Revenue (Tax payment).

Some of the frequently used celebrities in recent times include Tiwatope Savage-Balogun (Tiwa Savage), Olubankole Wellington (Banky W), Ayodeji Ibrahim Balogun (Wizkid), Funke Akindele, Broda Shaggi, Mercy Johnson, Ayodeji Richard Makun (A.Y), Kate Henshaw, Ali Nuhu, Genevieve Nnaji, etc. These celebrities have endorsement deals with several companies and products ranging from detergents, toothpaste, phones/gadgets, drinks, food, fashion items, stationaries, etc.

Advertisement through the use of celebrity endorsement has been found as a useful means of creating product awareness and perception in the minds of target customers (Martey & Frempong, 2014; Samar & Samreen, 2015). As a consumer surrounded by brands, there is exposure to millions of personalities on billboards and television. Every brand tries to capture the consumers' time and attention to inform them about what they have to offer and enlighten them about the different attributes of their product.

Research conducted by Verma and Kishore (2015) found that women are highly attracted to celebrity endorsement. They affirmed that women tend to purchase items or products that they see in advertisements. In the same vein, Biswas, Hussain and O'Donnell (2015) emphasised that people between the ages of 18-25 have the greatest ability to recall brands using celebrity endorsers compared with older age groups. It is against this background that understanding the influence of celebrity and testimonial advertising on buyers' behaviour toward Lush and Darling hair in Umuahia, Abia State is deemed critical.

Statement of the problem

The purchasing conduct and intention can be influenced by the image of endorsing a celebrity. Those are also contingent upon intrinsic and extrinsic factors, e.g. culture, psychology, society, family, educational background, economy, etc. Several studies, such as Erdogan (1999), Biswas, Biswas, and Das (2006), and Amos, Holmes, and Strutton (2008) have shown a progressive interest in the scope of this research field.

Creswell (2008) stated that "nothing sells like a celebrity" through advertising. Taylor (2016) on the hand emphasized that celebrity endorser in advertising is "not necessarily a recipe for success" and that ads with celebrities underperformed slightly. Also, the study of Tomkovik, Yelkur and Christians (2001) revealed that celebrities do not enhance ad likability. However, there remains a sustained interest in celebrity endorsement in the advertising industry (Whan & Parker, 2016). Based on these controversies, there is a need to validate the findings on the nexus between celebrity endorsement and consumer purchasing behaviour in the hair product industry.

Wilson and Chosniel (2013) stated that most of the studies on celebrity endorsement are mostly on the capabilities of the celebrity endorser. They have provided little direction regarding the impact those endorsements have on consumer purchasing behaviour. More so, discernments of brands and purchasing actions usually vary from one individual to another due to the influence of some other persons. It is based on these gaps identified above that this study wants to establish the influence of celebrity endorsement and testimonial adverts on changes in consumer purchasing behaviour among buyers of Lush and Darling hair in Umuahia, Abia State, taking into consideration the various attributes of celebrity endorsement and how each of these attributes affects consumer purchasing behaviour. While celebrity endorsement and testimonial adverts are good and generally accepted to sell the product advertised, how such testifiers and celebrity endorsements influence the buying behaviours of female users in Umuahia in Abia State is the prompting for this research.

Objectives of study

The central objective of the study is to examine the influence of celebrity and testimonial advertising on buyers' behaviour towards Lush and Darling hair in Umuahia, Abia State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the exposure level of buyers of Lush and Darling hair products to celebrity and testimonial advertisements.
2. Ascertain the extent to which celebrity and testimonial advertisements influence the interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products.
3. Determine the extent to which celebrity and testifier credibility shape the conviction of consumers and buying intention of lush and darling hair products.

4. Check the extent to which purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are based on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Research Question

The research is guided by the following research questions, serving as roadmaps:

1. To what extent are buyers of Lush and Darling hair products exposed to celebrity and testimonial advertisements?
2. To what extent do celebrity and testimonial advertisements influence the interest and recall of the buyer toward Lush and Darling hair products?
3. To what extent does celebrity and testifier credibility shape the conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products?
4. To what extent do purchases of Lush and Darling hair products based on celebrity and testimonial advertisements?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses have been formulated to test variables for statistical significance:

Hypothesis One

Ho: The interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products is not dependent on exposure level to celebrity and testimonial advertisements influence

Hi: The interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products is dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements influence

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is not significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

Hi: The conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

Hypothesis Three

Ho: The purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are not dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Hi: The purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are highly dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Significance of study

This research serves as a guide and successive-competitive tool for both the existing and emerging manufacturers and marketers in mapping out objectives and effective strategies with the consumer as the focal point.

The study would be of immense benefit to an organization's decision-making regarding celebrity endorsement for its product or service. Seeing the positive and negative effects of celebrity endorsement on consumers' behaviour towards Lush and Darling Hair will increase and motivate advertisers.

The findings of the study provide relevant insights to brand managers within the industry on the concept of celebrity endorsement and how it affects their brand and its influence on their consumer base and their client's bottom line.

Furthermore, it will be relevant for academic purposes. The rigorous nature of the methodology of this research will make it serve as a pedestal for advanced and continuous future research for students, market intelligence, research consultants and others. It will also serve as material for academic reference in the circles of marketing, advertising and strategic management treatment of the general topic of celebrity endorsements.

This research will be useful and relevant material to students, teachers and researchers of mass communication as a material for academic exercise and activities. While this study will serve as a foundation for further studies in the fields of marketing, advertising, visual communication and public relations, it will surely add to the volume of academic literature in this area of learning.

Literature Review

Historical and Current Perspective on Celebrity Endorsement

According to Adeyanju (2013), celebrities are people who enjoy public recognition possessing such attributes as attractiveness and trustworthiness. Celebrities are prominent and famous people who have excelled in their respective fields of endeavours and therefore command respect, acceptance, popularity and followership within society. Shamar and Prabhakar, (2013) also see celebrities as people who have certain characteristics which differentiate them from the common people. These characteristics are; popularity, high recognition in a society or culture, attention grabber and very famous in their respective faculties. According to Sanchez (2004), an endorser is a person who keenly supports or appears with a product or service in a way that is communicable to the public. Celebrity endorsers are individuals who enjoy public cognition and use this cognition on behalf of an advertiser by appearing with a product in an advertisement (Ranjbarian, Shekarchizade, and Momeni, 2010).

Due to the appealing status of celebrities in society, advertisers and product makers have developed an interest in them and used them as a way of entreating consumers to buy a product or subscribe to a service. Increased use of celebrities can be seen nowadays in advertising irrespective of the form of media. A celebrity can give a human dimension to an intangible or commodity product, most celebrities generate free publicity for the advertiser merely by their controversial association with the product. There is no doubt that celebrity advertising has its benefits; Quick saliency, Quick connection, Quick shorthand for brand values and easy brand differentiation. It is often perceived by organizations that feelings toward a celebrity are expected to transfer to the endorsed brand through their recurring association. The recurrent exposure to celebrity-endorsed advertisements activates the audience's memory by building an associative link between the audience and the product advertised by the celebrity. (Sharma & Prabhakar, 2013). Celebrity endorsement gives a brand a touch of glamour and the hope that a famous face will provide added appeal and name recognition in a crowded market. Companies spend hugely on celebrities to endorse their products or sponsored messages on the traditional and electronic media in the hope that such an endorsement will induce favourable attitudes towards the brand and ultimately affect sales and profits by increasing consumers' preference for the brand. (Erdogan & Baker, 2000).

Over the years many arguments have been done concerning the ideas of what makes celebrity endorsement a success. Many studies have also been conducted which are aimed at finding out all the factors that are very active to create an impact on the buying behaviour of consumers. According to a business and brand strategist, namely Martin Roll, he points out that there are three essential elements for celebrity endorsements. They are:

1. Attractiveness
2. Credibility and
3. Meaning transferred between the endorser and the brand

According to Roll, he says that a celebrity endorser should possess the quality that a target audience for that endorsed brand finds appealing. These qualities could be in terms of lifestyle or physical appearance may be intellectual capabilities. Roll explains the term credibility as the celebrity endorser's perceived trustworthiness and expertise. He quotes "as celebrity endorsement acts as an external cue that enables customers to see through the tremendous brand clutter in the market, the credibility factor of the celebrity greatly influences the acceptance with customers" (Roll) and his opinion about the transfer of meaning is that there has to be enough compatibility between the product and the celebrity.

Celebrity Endorsement as a Marketing Tool

When we talk in terms of the perspective of marketing communications, it becomes immensely vital to create such strategies that provide a competitive differential advantage to its products that result in creating positive effects in the consumer's mind. (Erdogan and Baker 1999) states that celebrity endorsement is the most widely used marketing strategy.

Companies spend a lot of money to hire celebrities to endorse their products, such celebrities are viewed by others as being dynamic, likeable and attractive. Marketers try to align these characteristics of celebrities with their products. According to Cooper 2014, advertisements that have celebrities gain a high degree of appeal, attention and recall rate than those advertisements without celebrities.

Colin (2018) states that celebrity endorsement brings about positive financial gains for the company. Many kinds of research have been conducted on the endorsements done by celebrities, many of which prove that this technique has provided the company with positive effects, but in some cases, researchers mention that celebrity endorsement doesn't work all the time and does not get the marketers their desired results. Sometimes the advertisements using celebrities do not meet up the expectations of the advertiser.

Marketing makes a priority the consumer (Reynolds & Lancaster, 2001). It focuses on its needs. It uses persuasion as a tool to compel the consumer to a promoted brand or product. It thrives to inject the ad into the consumer's mind creatively and repetitively. Celebrity-based ads communicate their content and aim for ad recall and brand appeal. Endorser holds a central role in the latter scheme by capturing the consumer's attention toward himself and the ad. Then, advertisement becomes for both endorser's image and brand. Soliciting celebrities for commercials became a known practice for leading companies and luxury brands (Rai & Sharma, 2013). The presence of celebrities might incur consequences on consumers relevant to their perception of the brand, their brand preferences, and their willingness to buy (Kumar, 2010).

Marketers refer to analytical studies before the selection of the celebrity endorser. An inappropriate choice of celebrity will cause the failure of communicating the intended message of the ad, hence the consumer's passive purchase intention (Farrell, Karels, Montfort, & McClatchey, 2000).

Consumer Purchasing Behaviour

Consumer Behaviour According to Pant (2007), consumer behaviour is the study of individuals, groups or organizations and the processes they use to select, secure, use and dispose of products, services,

experiences or ideas to satisfy needs and the impacts that these processes have on the consumer and society. Consumer behaviour is also defined as the study of how people buy, what they buy when they buy and why they buy. It refers to the buying process that occurs to anyone willing to buy, from individuals to households, groups or organisations (Kotler & Keller 2011). Consumer behaviours can be influenced by both internal and external stimuli. Some of the most common stimuli are personal factors, cultural factors and social factors. In addition, the consumer's factors such as perception, motivation, learning and memory comprise influence how the consumer responds to the marketing stimuli. (Kotler & Keller, 2007). Factors influencing consumer behaviour include economic factors, psychological factors, and sociological factors.

Every individual's consumer behaviour or purchase decision of the consumers can significantly be influenced by their buying habits which are affected by technological, political, demographic, cultural, economic, personal, psychological, and social factors, et cetera. These factors are revealed or shown in the attitude, drive, perception, disposition, knowledge, and lifestyle of the consumers.

Celebrity endorsement plays a significant role in arousing these various factors, more especially the psychological motive of the consumer to buy a particular product and inspire consumers to repurchase these brands of goods. Consequently, consumers are fascinated by the brand of products which are passionately attached to their behaviours and it builds into customer loyalty (Osifo & Agbonifoh, 2018). Samar and Samreen (2015) establish that emotional affection put a significant effect on consumers and their purchasing behaviour as individuals tend to link themselves with the brand of products endorsed by celebrities. Celebrity endorsement influences the behaviours of consumers to buy a specific product through cognition. These perceptions are perceived by consumers through their senses, discernment, attention, recall, reasoning, language, et cetera (Samar & Samreen, 2015). To this end, a celebrity endorsement is a significant approach to changing the buying plans of individuals.

Empirical Review

There are related studies done on the link between celebrity endorsement and consumer purchasing behaviour. Mowemi (2013) examined the influence of celebrity endorsement and brand awareness on consumers' purchase decisions: a comparative study of yoyo bitters and alomo bitters. The major objective of this study is to measure the extent to which celebrity endorsement influences consumers' perception of Yoyo Bitters and Alomo Bitters. Also, the study wishes to find out the relationship, if there is any that exists between product types, choice of a celebrity endorser, and celebrity's personality. A total number of one hundred and seventy copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the consumers within the Ibadan metropolis. Based on the findings of the study, it is obvious that celebrity endorsement plays a vital role in disseminating advertisement information that can influence consumers to make rational choices on products and services.

Nyakado (2013) in a study of the relationship between celebrity endorsement and consumer behaviour using a representative sample size of 300 respondents established that the physical attractiveness of a celebrity affects consumers toward buying a particular brand of products. He suggested that companies should not only seek the services of a celebrity who is only popular but also who has credibility. The findings of the study revealed that celebrity-endorsed brands have a propensity to attract more consumers.

Osewe (2013) conducted a study on the effectiveness of Internet commercials on consumer purchasing behaviour using a stratified sampling technique to select 100 respondents. He established that Internet commercials have a significant link with buying choice of consumers. He concluded that Internet commercials are effective in reaching and creating consciousness in the minds of consumers.

Theoretical Framework

This study is situated within and around the frameworks of Reference Group Theory and The Source Credibility Theory.

Reference group theory: The theory appropriately linked celebrity endorsement attributes and consumer purchasing behaviour as the exogenous and dependent variables respectively in this study. The model postulates that a certain imaginary person or group is considered to have a substantial influence on another person's assessment, drives, and behaviour (Whan & Parker, 2016). It argues that consumers tend to look out for a brand of products confirmed to have affirmative credibility by a neutral professional. This helps to affirm consumers existing awareness of a brand (Whan & Parker, 2016). Therefore, the reference group theory is of the position that most consumers see celebrities as highly reliable sources of confirmation of their knowledge of a product.

Furthermore, the reference group theory maintains that consumers need certain celebrity similarities in a buying situation; otherwise, it is risky to purchase that brand of products. Looking for a match to what another person or reference group approves is relevant when making a repurchase decision (Whan & Parker, 2016). A celebrity endorsing a product can be a source of utilitarian influence on consumers who desire conformity in a purchase situation (McGuire, 2013).

Lastly, according to the reference group theory, consumers look out for a match between themselves and an individual or group of individuals considered to be proficient and share something in common. This may be in the form of buying the brand of products used or those prescribed by the group of individuals considered to be proficient. An optimistic self-image is relevant since a consumer is more eager to be related to good folks instead of bad folks (Whan & Parker, 2016). In other words, consumers see celebrities as positive referents and can therefore seek consistency with celebrities endorsing a product.

The Source Credibility Theory: The Source Credibility Theory was expounded by Carl Hovland (1953). This theory seeks to view credibility as the extent to which consumers view the source of the advertising message. They see it as the source having concrete and viable knowledge alongside possessing efficient and effective skills plus the experience needed to provide objective information.

Source Credibility has become a term commonly used to imply a communicator's positive characteristics that affect the receiver's acceptance of a message (Okanagan, 1990). The Source Credibility Theory highlights the importance of worthy ideals embodied by the source of messages to hold credibility. The source according to Belch & Belch (2012), is the person that is involved in the communication of the advertising messages, they can be direct or indirect. A direct source is a spokesperson that delivers a message or endorses the product while an indirect source does not deliver the message but draws attention and adds appeal to the advertisement.

The theory was derived from a study that was carried out by Hovland, Janis and Kelly (1953), which stipulates the necessary factors, which underline the credibility of a source are Trustworthiness, Expertise and Attractiveness. In light of the above-mentioned, the characteristic of the source/celebrity must be tested to help determine the credibility and the acceptance of the messages embedded in the Darling and Lush hair products advertisement.

This theory is congruent with this current study as it explains how the credibility of the celebrity used by Darling and Lush hair products can influence the acceptance of the testimonial and celebrity advertising messages by the users. It is important as it shows the degree of interactivity between the credibility of the

celebrity used by Darling and Lush hair products in their advertising and the acceptance of the advertisement messages by the consumer.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design, with a focus on the survey research method. The population of the study consists of female residents of the Umuahia metropolis in Abia State. The population of the study, therefore, is 257,589(2022 Projected Estimates) based on the 2006 Population and Housing Census. Because of the largeness of the population (257,589), a sample of 384 was drawn using the *SmartSurvey* online sample size calculator.

The random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample frame in which information was collected from six communities within the 2 L.G.A.s in the Umuahia metropolis.

A breakdown of this is shown in the table below.

Table 3.5.1: Equal Representation of Selected Communities by L.G.A in Umuahia Metropolis

L.G.A	Layout	Population Projection	Sample Size	Study Area
Umuahia North	Umuagu	157,192	234	78
	Umukabia			78
	Ohuhu			78
Umuahia South	Apumiri	100,397	150	50
	Olokoru			50
	Ohia			50
		257,589	384	

Source: Field Data, 2022

Considering the sample size, a questionnaire was used as a standard measurement tool to obtain data from the respondents. The questionnaire contained questions that relate to the subject matter of the influence of celebrity and testimonial advertising on buyer's behaviour. A study of Lush and Darling hair in Umuahia, Abia State.

Testing of Hypotheses

To speculate on the outcome of this research and to test for the statistical significance of collected research data, the following hypothetical statements were tested for statistical significance.

The researchers used the Chi-square formula as the statistical instrument for testing the two hypotheses raised in the study. The formula states

$$X = \sum \frac{(of - ef)^2}{ef}$$

Where

of	=	observed frequency
ef	=	expected frequency
Σ	=	summation

χ^2 distribution is worked out by the value of its degree of freedom (df). To achieve this, a contingency table is used.

Decision Rule: Accept the research hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis if the calculated value is greater than the critical or table value.

Hypothesis One

- Ho: The interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products is not dependent on exposure level to celebrity and testimonial advertisements influence
- Hi: The interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products is dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements influence

Contingency Analysis

Here, research data presented in Table X and Table IX were used for contingency analysis.

Table XXI: (Contingency): The interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darlinghair products is dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements influence (Merged Data from Table X and Table IX)

RESPONSE	INTEREST AND RECALL		EXPOSURE LEVEL		TOTAL
	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	
1	357	214	71	214	428
2	0	124	248	124	248
3	17	29	41	29	58
4	0	7	14	7	14
Total	374		374		748

The figures in brackets are the expected frequencies

$$Fe = \frac{TR \times TC}{GT}$$

Expected Frequency Calculation

$$ER = \frac{\text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}}{\text{Grand Total}}$$

Row 1 Cell 1	374 x 428	÷	748	=	214
Row 1 Cell 2	374 x 248	÷	748	=	124
Row 1 Cell 3	374 x 58	÷	748	=	29
Row 1 Cell 4	374 x 14	÷	748	=	7
Row 2 Cell 1	374 x 428	÷	748	=	214
Row 2 Cell 2	374 x 248	÷	748	=	124
Row 2 Cell 3	374 x 58	÷	748	=	29
Row 2 Cell 4	374 x 14	÷	748	=	7

XXII: Chi-square Testing of Hypothesis One

of	ef	of - ef	(of - ef) ²	(of - ef) ² ef
357	214	143	20449	95.55
0	124	-124	15376	124

17	29	-12	144	4.96
0	7	-7	49	7
71	214	-143	20449	95.55
248	124	124	15376	124
41	29	12	144	4.96
14	7	7	49	7
748				463.02

χ^2 = value calculated = **463.02**

Degree of freedom (df): To find the degree of freedom (4 rows and 2 columns)

$$df = (R - 1) (C - 1)$$

$$(4 - 1) (2 - 1)$$

$$3 \times 1 = 3$$

$$df = 3$$

Level of significance = 5% = 0.05

Test Result: At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is 7.815. Since the *Table Value* (7.815) is less than the calculated value (**463.02**), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products are dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements' influence.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is not significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

Hi: The conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

Contingency Analysis

Here, research data presented in **Table XII** and **Table XI** were used for contingency analysis.

Table XXIII: (Contingency): Conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility. (Merged Data from Table XII and Table XI)

RESPONSE	CONVICTION AND BUYING INTENTION		TRUST OF CELEBRITIES AND TESTIFIERS		TOTAL
	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	
1	335	336	337	336	672
2	24	24	24	24	48
3	15	14	13	14	28
Total	374		374		748

The figures in brackets are the expected frequencies

$$Fe = \frac{TR \times TC}{GT}$$

Expected Frequency Calculation

$$ER = \text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}$$

Grand Total

Row 1	Cell 1	374 x 672	÷	748	=	336
Row 1	Cell 2	374 x 48	÷	748	=	24
Row 1	Cell 3	374 x 28	÷	748	=	14
Row 2	Cell 1	374 x 672	÷	748	=	336
Row 2	Cell 2	374 x 48	÷	748	=	24
Row 2	Cell 3	374 x 28	÷	748	=	14

XXIV: Chi-square Testing of Hypothesis Two

of	ef	of - ef	(of - ef) ²	(of - ef) ² ef
335	336	-1	1	0.0029
24	24	0	0	0
15	14	1	1	0.071
337	336	1	1	0.0029
24	24	0	0	0
13	14	-1	1	0.071
748				0.1478

χ^2 = value calculated = **0.1478**

Degree of freedom (df): To find the degree of freedom (3 rows and 2 columns)

$$df = (R - 1) (C - 1)$$

$$(3 - 1) (2 - 1)$$

$$2 \times 1 = 2$$

$$df = 2$$

Level of significance = 5% = 0.05

Test Result: At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is 7.815. Since the *Table Value* (5.991) is less than the calculated value (**0.1478**), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

Hypothesis Three

- Ho: The purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are not dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.
- Hi: The purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are highly dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Contingency Analysis

Here, research data presented in Table XIV and Table XV were used for contingency analysis.

Table XXV: (Contingency): Conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility. (Merged Data from Table XIV and Table XV)

RESPONSE	USED OF LUSH OR/AND DARLING HAIR		INFLUENCED OF ADVERTISEMENTS		TOTAL
	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	Freq. Obsv.	Freq. Expd.	
1	269	259.5	250	259.5	519
2	19	19	19	19	38
3	79	88.5	98	88.5	177
4	7	7	7	7	14
Total	374		374		748

The figures in brackets are the expected frequencies

$$E_{fe} = \frac{TR \times TC}{GT}$$

Expected Frequency Calculation

$$E_{fe} = \frac{\text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}}{\text{Grand Total}}$$

Row 1 Cell 1	374×519	\div	748	$=$	259.5
Row 1 Cell 2	374×38	\div	748	$=$	19
Row 1 Cell 3	374×177	\div	748	$=$	88.5
Row 1 Cell 4	374×14	\div	748	$=$	7
Row 2 Cell 1	374×519	\div	748	$=$	259.5
Row 2 Cell 2	374×38	\div	748	$=$	19
Row 2 Cell 3	374×177	\div	748	$=$	88.5
Row 2 Cell 4	374×14	\div	748	$=$	7

XXVI: Chi-square Testing of Hypothesis Two

of	Ef	of - ef	(of - ef) ²	$\frac{(of - ef)^2}{ef}$
269	259.5	9.5	90.25	0.347
19	19	0	0	0
79	88.5	-9.5	90.25	1.019
7	7	0	0	0
250	259.5	-9.5	90.25	0.347
19	19	0	0	0
98	88.5	9.5	90.25	1.019
7	7	0	0	0
748				2.732

χ^2 = value calculated = 2.732

Degree of freedom (df): To find the degree of freedom (4 rows and 2 columns)

$$\begin{aligned}df &= (R - 1) (C - 1) \\ &= (4 - 1) (2 - 1) \\ &= 3 \times 1 = 3 \\ df &= 3\end{aligned}$$

Level of significance = 5% = 0.05

Test Result: At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is 7.815. Since the *Table Value* (7.815) is less than the calculated value (2.732), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are highly dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Discussion of Results

This study provides many interesting results to be discussed. All three hypotheses were accepted. Data presented in *Table VI* shows that all the respondents claimed to have exposure the various advertising media. Impliedly, they have watched television, listened to the radio, or read various newspapers and magazines. Also, research data presented in *Table VII* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (236 representing 63.1%) have multimedia advertising exposure. However, 39 or 10.4% have exposure to Radio; 14 or 3.7% have exposure to Television; 4 or 1.1% have exposure to newspapers/Magazines; 65 or 17.4% have exposure to Social Media, while Billboards and Salesforce have 8 representing 2.1% exposures respectively.

Research data as presented in *Table VIII* shows that all the 374 respondents claimed to have encountered celebrity and testimonial advertisements on either Lush or/and Darling hair products. Impliedly, this research data shows provides the prerequisites for possible influence. Data presented in *Table IX* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (248 representing 66.3%) have sometimes been exposed to celebrity and testimonial advertisements on Lush and Darling hair products. However, 71 or 19% have frequently been exposed to celebrity and testimonial advertisements on Lush and Darling hair products. While 41 or 11% have rarely been exposed to celebrity and testimonial advertisements on Lush and Darling hair products; 14 or 3.7% were indifferent. This data represents the chief determinants of influence on the buyers.

Research data presented in *Table X* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (357 representing 95.5%) claimed that the celebrity and testimonial advertisements make them remember and influence their interest in the Lush and Darling hair products. While none of the respondents differed; 17 or 4.5% were undecided. Implying, therefore, that celebrity and testimonial advertisements can indeed cause remembrance while influencing the interest of women and ladies in the Lush and Darling hair products. Also, collected research data as presented in *Table XI* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (337 representing 90.1%) claimed that they trust the celebrities used in advertising and testifying about the Lush and Darling hair products. While 24 or 6.4% of the respondents differed, 13 or 5.5% were undecided. The implication, therefore, is that women and lady users trust the celebrities used in advertising and testifiers about the Lush and Darling hair products. Such trust is what influences patronage.

Research data collected as presented in *Table XII* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (335 representing 89.6%) claimed the credibility of celebrities and testifiers used in advertising Lush and Darling Hair Products does shape their conviction and intention to buy. While 24 or 6.4% of the respondents differed, 15 or 4% were undecided. The implication is that the credibility of celebrities and testifiers plays a key role in shaping ladies' and women users' convictions and intentions to buy such advertised products like Lush and Darling Hair.

Data collected as presented in *Table XIII* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (251 or 67.1%) claimed that they have been influenced to patronise Lush or/and Darling hair products; 24 others, representing 6.4% of the respondents claimed they have not been influenced to patronise Lush or/and Darling hair products. However, 84 or 22.5% of the respondents claimed they have somehow been influenced to patronise Lush or/and Darling hair products, but a minority of the respondents (15 representing 4%) were indifferent. The inference adducible from this data is that adverts with celebrity and testifying messages have a great influence on the patronage of products such as Lush or/and Darling Hair.

Data collected as presented in *Table XIV* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (269 or 71.9%) claimed that they have bought and used either the Lush or/and Darling hair products; 19 others, representing 5.1% of the respondents claimed they have not bought and used either the Lush or/and Darling hair products. However, 79 or 21.1% of the respondents claimed they have somehow bought and used either the Lush or/and Darling hair products, but a minority of the respondents (7 representing 1.9%) were indifferent.

Data collected as presented in *Table XV* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (250 or 66.8%) claimed that their decision to purchase Lush or/and Darling hair products was based on influences from celebrity and testimonial advertisements of the products; 19 representing 5.1% of the respondents claimed that their purchase of Lush or/and Darling hair products were never as a result of influences from celebrity and testimonial advertisements of the products. However, 98 or 26.2% of the respondents claimed that their decision to purchase Lush or/and Darling hair products was somehow based on influences from celebrities and testimonial advertisements of the products. However, a minority of the respondents (7 representing 1.9%) were indifferent. Impliedly, celebrity and testimonial advertisements have a significant influence on the buying behaviour of women and young ladies who use hair products as advertised.

Data collected as presented in *Table XVI* shows that out of the 374 respondents, the majority of them (250 or 66.8%) claimed that celebrity and testimonial advertisements are an effective tool for the marketing of Lush or/and Darling hair products; while 19 representing 5.1% of the respondents differed, 98 or 26.2% of the respondents claimed that celebrity and testimonial advertisements are somehow an effective tool for the marketing of Lush or/and Darling hair products. However, a minority of the respondents (7 representing 1.9%) were indifferent. Impliedly, it is established that celebrity and testimonial advertisements are effective tools for the marketing of products such as Lush or/and Darling hair.

Research data in *Table XX* points to the fact that testimonial advertisements are more persuasive than celebrity advertisements. This is because, the majority of respondents (209 or 55.9%) agreed that testimonial advertisements are more persuasive than celebrity advertisements, while 117 or 31.3% strongly agreed that testimonial advertisements are more persuasive than celebrity advertisements. However, 12 or 3.2% disagreed; 29 or 7.7% strongly disagreed, while 7 or 1.9% of them were indifferent. This data imply that testimonial advertisements are more persuasive than celebrity advertisements as used in advertising Lush or/and Darling hair products.

For hypothesis one, research data presented in *Table X* and *Table IX* were used for contingency analysis. At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is

7.815. Since the *Table Value* (7.815) is less than the calculated value (463.02), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products are dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements' influence.

In hypothesis two, research data presented in Table XII and Table XI were used for contingency analysis. At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is 7.815. Since the *Table Value* (5.991) is less than the calculated value (0.1478), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.

For Hypothesis Three, research data presented in Table XIV and Table XV were used for contingency analysis. At 0.05 probability level or 95% confidence level and degree of freedom placed at 3, the table value is 7.815. Since the *Table Value* (7.815) is less than the calculated value (2.732), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This, therefore, means that the purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are highly dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.

Summary of Findings

Various findings, based on data analysis are hereby summarized:

1. Evidence from research data shows that women and ladies in Umuahia have used multimedia advertising exposure to encounter celebrity and testimonial advertisements on Lush or/and Darling hair products.
2. Celebrity endorser credibility and testifier have a positive effect on consumers' advertisement recall and purchase intention for Lush and Darling hair products.
3. Data also reveals that the conviction of consumers and their buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products is significantly related to the celebrity and testifier's credibility.
4. Also, data points out that respondents have not only been influenced but have bought and used the Lush or/and Darling hair products. Implying further that the purchases of Lush and Darling hair products are highly dependent on celebrity and testimonial advertisements.
5. Research confirms the fact that celebrity and testimonial advertisements are effective tools for the marketing of Lush or/and Darling hair products, revealing further that testimonial advertisements are more persuasive than celebrity advertisements.
6. Evidence of research data also shows that the interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products are dependent on exposure level to celebrities and testimonial advertisements influence.

Conclusion

From the result of the study, there exists a positive and significant link between celebrity endorsement and consumer purchasing behaviour of women who patronize hair products in the Umuahia metropolis in Abia State. Given the above, we have come to the reasoned conclusion that it will be easy for product manufacturers, wholesalers and retailers of hair products to influence the purchasing behaviour of consumers. This can be done through the building of consciousness and sustainable insight in the minds of their consumers using celebrity endorsement, more especially the celebrities that are trustworthy, attractive, and with the requisite expertise.

Recommendations

Having examined the influence of celebrity and testimonial advertising on buyer's behaviour toward Lush and Darling hair products in Umuahia, Abia State, the following policy recommendations are made based on research data:

1. To remain successful and competitive, hair product marketers should aggressively implement the use of celebrity endorsement attributes in the advertisement of their products as a business strategy.
2. Firms should use more celebrity endorsements to build consciousness and perceptions of their products in the minds of consumers. Celebrities should be provided with more information regarding the company's brand and product to build buyers' awareness and perception of their products.
3. Advertising agencies and makers of products and services should intensify their efforts to put celebrities to proper scrutiny in terms of character, personality, popularity, and human relations before they can be allowed to authorize their products and services.
4. Managers should devise suitable strategies to identify the right celebrity endorsement attributes that would lead to improved competitiveness as the combined effect is greater than the use of one attribute.
5. Hair product marketers should watch out for celebrities that are trustworthy as a majority of customers make purchases because of the high level of honesty and trust reposed in celebrities.
6. The attractiveness of celebrities is also of great virtue in the endorsement of a product as more consumers tend to be influenced by their virtuous features such as intellectual skills, sportsmanship, and charm, before purchasing a product or service.
7. The similarities between the celebrity and its target market should be considered such as putting into consideration the age, gender and culture of the celebrity to its target market. In some cases, individuals tend to favour and appreciate celebrities who share common features and traits with them.

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